

SOCIAL SCIENCES

PITIRIM SOROKIN'S HERITAGE: CORE IDEAS ON SOCIAL SOLIDARITY

Batovrina E.,

*Candidate of Sociological Sciences, Associate Professor at Human Resource Department,
School of Public Administration, Lomonosov Moscow State University,
Moscow, Russia*

Mikhaylova O.

*Doctor of Political Sciences, Professor at Policy Analysis Department,
School of Public Administration, Lomonosov Moscow State University,
Moscow, Russia*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7878749>

Abstract

The formation of social solidarity ties is one of the key problems on the agenda of the governments of the modern states. The world practice shows that it is impossible to solve it once and for all. In many ways, this is why the solidarity has been the object of interest of sociologists for many decades. The ideas of social solidarity, mostly having their foundations in the works of the classics of sociology A. Comte, H. Spencer, F. Giddings, E. Durkheim, T. Parsons, and others, are widely known. The contribution of the Russian pre-revolutionary sociologists and philosophers to the development of the ideas of social solidarity turned out to be on the periphery of science. Pitirim Sorokin, who considered solidarity in three hypostases – as a form of organization of society, as a manifestation of altruism in interpersonal and intergroup relations and as a sign of constructive social behavior, is the only Russian sociologist regularly mentioned in a number of authoritative authors who proposed an alternative understanding of the principles and origins of the formation of solidarity ties. His ideas about them resonate with the ideas of the other Russian thinkers (P. Kropotkin, P. Lavrov, M. Bakunin, N. Mikhaylovsky, N. Kareev), who defined social solidarity as a manifestation of social initiative and ‘the engine of social progress’, a resource for social mobilization and a factor of achieving social justice and resisting pressure of state.

The purpose of the article is to reveal the main provisions of the concept of social solidarity of Sorokin as the quintessence of the ideas of solidarity ties developed in the Russian pre-revolutionary sociology. The concept of Sorokin and the ideas of the Russian sociologists and philosophers that definitely influenced on its development laid the foundation for the further analysis of social solidarity and its formation as a phenomenon and process coming ‘from below’, depending on the behavior and will of each member of society. These ideas turned out to be consonant with the tendencies in the modern Russian society which is making the real efforts to strengthen the social ties in the circumstances of the deficit of state policy in this sphere.

Keywords: Pitirim Sorokin, social solidarity, Russian pre-revolutionary sociology, social ties

Introduction

Pitirim Alexandrovich Sorokin (1889–1968) was an outstanding Russian and American sociologist, whose unique personality had been shaped by the harsh everyday life of the Russian north in Vologda province (modern Komi Republic). His political views led him to the camp of the supporters of the anti-tsarist revolution and then the fight against the Bolsheviks. Sorokin made the first important scientific steps at Petrograd University, but it was in exile that he became a prominent scientist in sociology. In 1922, Sorokin was expelled from the country along with other eminent representatives of the Russian science and culture on board the so-called ‘Philosophers’ ship’³. For him, the exile was a substitute for the death penalty.

Not experiencing a creative fatigue, working intensively for eight years since leaving Soviet Russia, overcoming rejection and distrust on the part of American academic community, in 1930, Sorokin accepted an invitation to head the Department of Sociology at

Harvard University. He led it for an unusually long time, until 1959. That was the period that is considered the pinnacle of Sorokin's scientific work, when he not only published all new books and articles, but when they gained worldwide recognition and turned him into a prominent scientist in sociology.

Throughout his scientific career Sorokin published 37 books and more than 400 articles. However, despite the fact that his individual theoretical developments were widely recognized, Sorokin never created his own scientific school in the United States. Sorokin's famous colleague T. Parsons became a more influential researcher in the academic world. His theoretical generalizations corresponded to the ideas of the Russian sociologist, but there were serious contradictions between them at the interpersonal level, they prevented their collaboration. Sorokin's student R. Merton gained worldwide recognition, but mainly due to the fact that he started his research in line with Parson's, not So-

³ ‘Philosophers’ ship’ is a collective term for several voyages of passenger steamboats that transported more than 250 Russian intellectuals out of Soviet Russia.

rokin's theoretical framework. The eccentricity of Sorokin's speeches and scientific works led him into academic isolation in the second half of the 1950s – 1960s. However, in 1964, he was elected chairman of the American Sociological Association, thus recognizing Sorokin's outstanding contribution to social science. Pitirim Sorokin died in 1968, entering the history of Russian and American science as one of the founders of theoretical sociology.

Sorokin is well-known for his theories of social stratification and mobility, his ideas on social solidarity are shadowed by the ones of European classics of sociology such as O. Comte, E. Durkheim, etc. In his works, Sorokin conceptualized solidarity atypically for the European and American scientific tradition. He treated it within the framework of the pre-revolutionary Russian school of sociology characterized by the study of social phenomena on normative and value foundations, not in terms of positivism that dominated science. Sorokin's theoretical assumptions on the origins of social solidarity were greatly affected by N. Mikhailovsky, P. Lavrov, N. Kareev, M. Kovalevsky, P. Kropotkin and M. Bakunin. His ideas were also significantly influenced by his personal background – first of all by his early childhood spent among the Komi people. He admired them for endurance that got roots from the need to physically survive in many months of cold winter, mutual assistance and social inequality minimized.

Solidarity as a leading factor of social progress in scientific works of Russian pre-revolutionary social thinkers

Unlike European sociology, Russian sociology predominantly developed in terms of subjectivism, not positivism. *Nikolai Mikhailovsky* (1842 – 1904), a prominent representative of *narodnichestvo*⁴, is considered the founder of Russian subjective sociology. He believed that sociology began with the creation of a *social ideal* that guided the researcher in their investigation of different social phenomena. Solidarity plays a major role in his social reflections, since with its growth, society develops and prospers, and its loss leads to a tougher struggle of people for survival and to social regression. Mikhailovsky closely links solidarity with the simple cooperation between equal and independent people in a society where there is no division of labour, and where the common goal causes mutual understanding and mutual assistance. This ideal, he believed, is achievable in a peasant community, where the personality triumphs with the help of community. In contrast to this ideal, class division, division of labour, and guild cooperativity undermine the integrity of society, suppress the individuality, give rise to differentiation of roles and statuses, legal and political institutions are formed to create social unity and protect it. Social solidarity, therefore, is attainable in societies that guarantee the freedom of the individual, their independence and personal development.

A society strengthened by solidarity ties appears as an ideal in the works of another outstanding representative of Russian social science, *Nikolai Kareev* (1850–1931). He contributed to the career advancement and scientific development of Sorokin in Russia. Kareev also believed that the strengthening of solidarity is the main criterion for progress. The society goes through several stages in its development: from primitive communities with a lack of freedom and the dominance of force through societies dominated by legal methods of self-organization, to an ideal society dominated by solidarity, truth and justice. He derives a 'formula of progress', which is based on three elements: the goal of progress is development of the individual, their deliverance from various types of addictions by improving situation in society; the way to achieve the goal is through critical reshaping of the social organization of society, its culture and way of life; self-liberation of the individual (Kareev, 1897).

While studying at the St. Petersburg Psychoneurological Institute, Sorokin was noticed by a jurist, sociologist of law *Mikhail Kovalevsky* (1851–1916), and was left by him to prepare for a professorship at the department of criminal law. At one time, Sorokin even was his personal secretary, and after the death of Kovalevsky, he published several memoirs about the scientist's creative path, participated in the creation of the Russian Sociological Society named after Kovalevsky, which served as the basis for launching the Faculty of Sociology at Petrograd University in 1919.

In his scientific works, Kovalevsky developed a sociological approach to law, emphasizing its close ties with social phenomena and history of society. The emergence of law, from his point of view, is associated not with the state, but with the spread of social solidarity in the primitive group. He views solidarity as people's awareness of common interests and mutual dependence on each other that generate unity and serve as a driving force of social progress.

At an early stage of social development, solidarity arises from people's ideas about kinship and is a necessary factor of their survival. Later it is supported by the repressive nature of the norms that determine the range of freedom of action of members of a social group. Accordingly, the norms that ensure social solidarity are the norms of law based on the idea of duty, forcing individuals to assume obligations to realize the common interest of the group. The development of law occurs due to the development of social relations, and the progress of society is carried out through the growth of social solidarity from blood unity through patriotism to the highest stage of development, cosmopolitanism. At the same time, solidarity is based on the coordination of the interests of society and the individual, as well as various social groups, it ensures the optimal ratio of the individual freedom and the freedom of other members of the group, their rights and obligations. Its dynamics is associated with the expansion and consolidation of

⁴ *Narodnichestvo* is a direction in the Russian revolutionary movement of the second half of the 19th century. It is associated with the idea of convergence of the intelligentsia and the common people, idealizing the peasant community, speaking

out both against serfdom and the capitalist development model for the overthrow of the autocracy through either a peasant revolution or social transformations on the basis of the peasant community.

social ties between individuals and, as a result, the expansion of the boundaries of the ‘*pacified environment*’ – a space where the struggle was eliminated, and peace, interdependence and common interests were cultivated. The maintenance and development of solidarity is facilitated by the law – ‘the norms brought into life by the organized force of society which is the state, and serving the implementation of the tasks of social solidarity’ (Kovalevskiy 1909: 74).

Pyotr Kropotkin (1842–1921), a historian, philosopher, publicist and one of the most influential theorists of anarchism, had a significant influence on the development of Sorokin's ideas on social solidarity. Many researchers of the latter's work call him ‘the apostle of solidarity’ (Kritskaya 1931). This definition is not accidental. Kropotkin considered solidarity the main source of the productive development of mankind, and the basis for the realization of the creative potential and strength of people: solidarity is ‘a great engine that increases the energy and creative power of a person a hundredfold’ (Kropotkin 1919: 288). In many ways idealizing the phenomenon of solidarity, he put it on a par with true friendship, mutual assistance, equality, prosperity and satisfaction of the needs of all members of society without exception: ‘When there are no more rich and poor, when the hungry no longer have to look with envy at the well-fed, – then the real innate friendship can appear again between people; and then the religion of reciprocity and solidarity will replace that indefinite religion that draws its blurry images on the mists of the firmament’ (Kropotkin 1919: 18).

Kropotkin considered the centralized state power the main obstacle on the way to the development of solidarity in society. The absorption of all social functions by the state favoured, in his opinion, the development of narrow individualism, the desire to satisfy only personal needs without regard to the others and thereby acquire freedom. However, as Kropotkin notes, ‘without the cooperation of all an individual is powerless, no matter how full of gold their chests are’. He sees mutual assistance and cooperation as key manifestations of human solidarity, contributing to social evolution and progress: ‘the social practice of mutual assistance and its consistent development created the specific conditions of social life, thanks to which a person was able to develop his or her crafts and arts, science and mind; and we see that the periods when the institutions aimed at mutual assistance reached their highest development were also the periods of the greatest progress in arts, industry and science’ (Kropotkin 1907: 298).

Kropotkin's ideas on social solidarity are close to the ideas of the philosopher, theorist of anarchism *Mikhail Bakunin* (1814–1876). He defined social solidarity as ‘the first human law’. At the same time, Bakunin believed that solidarity coexists with freedom, which constitutes the ‘second human law’: ‘Both of these laws complement each other and, being inseparable from one another, constitute the whole essence of humanity. Thus, freedom is not a negation of solidarity, on the contrary, it represents the development and, if I may say so, the humanization of the latter’ (Bakunin 2016: 103). Like Kropotkin, Bakunin viewed the state as the main obstacle in the formation and development of solidarity

ties, he believed that social solidarity and freedom could be fully achieved only through the destruction of the state. He also believed that the state is the power of a minority, which prevents the formation of solidarity among people and contradicts human morality. However, he did not deny any statehood, but advocated the abolition of authoritarian states with violent discipline and order.

Sorokin did not ignore the ideas of one of the first Russian sociologists, philosopher, historian, publicist *Pyotr Lavrov* (1823 – 1900) either. He devoted several articles to his scientific works, including the article ‘The main problems of P.L. Lavrov's sociology’, in which he paid special attention to his theory of solidarity and the factors of social solidarity identified by him (Sorokin 1922). Lavrov's works are devoted to the search for a social ideal and the clarification of the subject of sociology. Sociology, according to Lavrov, studies the conditions for the emergence of solidarity. One of the tasks of sociology is to reveal the dependence between strengthening or weakening of solidarity and specific historical conditions, as well as to clarify the relationship between strengthening or weakening of solidarity and the level of personal development. Lavrov believes that a high level of solidarity is an expression of a social ideal. The main sign of a high level of solidarity is ‘a strong sense of closeness among individuals in the same group’ (Lavrov 1898: 33). Lavrov distinguishes two more forms, or levels of solidarity – instinctive solidarity and heartfelt solidarity. The transition from one level to another takes place within and under the influence of the historical process.

Sorokin's understanding of solidarity and social interactions

Pitirim Sorokin became the successor of the typical Russian orientation of social thought and humanistic tradition characterized by an appeal to ethical categories, spiritual and moral aspects of human life. He views solidarity in this context and considers it the main ethical category and the key determinant of the conflict-free and progressive development of society. He contrasts solidarity with (1) *antagonistic interaction*, characterized by confrontation between participants, in which they mutually interfere with each other in achieving their goals, when one side seeks to make the other proceed in the direction that it he or she opposes; (2) *coercive social ties* that increase the antagonism of the participants in the interaction and contribute to the spread of hostility in society, in which one, forcing, side has complete freedom of action, and the other, coerced, side has no freedom at all.

In Sorokin's opinion, solidarity is a type of social interaction in which the expectations and actions of the participants coincide, and they mutually help each other in achieving their goals. The development of solidarity ties occurs through the strengthening of interactions, where one side seeks to induce the other to such actions that he or she is willing to perform himself or herself. In other words, solidarity doesn't result from people's subordination to the rules set ‘from above’ for weaving selfishly minded and competing individuals into a single network of social relations, but results from people's awareness of the commonality of their goals and

their unity, regardless of institutional coercion, and perhaps even contrary to it. Solidarity involves the achievement of the group goals by an individual as his or her own and the desire to satisfy the needs of other members of this group without external reward.

It is obvious that Sorokin's understanding of solidarity is based on a certain *ideal of social interaction* that involves doing good to other people as well as to oneself, avoiding harming them. This ideal is also related to an obvious religious connotation. Sorokin repeatedly refers to the fact that the main world religions call people to boundless altruistic love. And the ideal social organization for him is the peasant community that developed in the northern provinces of the Russian Empire, from which he himself was a native. There has never been slavery or serfdom in this region, and the community functioned on the principles of mutual assistance and self-government. The interaction of the community members was built not on egoistic and rational motives, but on altruistic ones. It is altruism that is considered by Sorokin to be an invariable companion of solidarity and key factor of its development. As a child, while studying at a parochial school, he read the biographies of many saints, whose ideals and deeds became an example of self-sacrifice and altruism for him. In his scientific works, he assigned the leading role in uniting and expanding solidarity ties to morally gifted individuals.

In social interaction, alongside the participants and their actions, *conductors* were particularly important for Sorokin. Thanks to them reactions, thoughts, irritation emanating from some individuals are transmitted and reach others (Sorokin 2008: 131). *Physical conductors* and *symbolic conductors* not only provide for the interaction of people with each other, unite them, and maintain collective and cultural unity, but also tie generations. Material culture is a combination of physical and symbolic conductors of interaction. The centuries-old human interaction accumulates and freezes in the material culture that surrounds each individual and transmits 'irritations that emanated from generations that once lived, and determines our experiences and actions in a very definite way' (Sorokin 2008: 157). The effect of the first-type conductors on people is limited exclusively to physical effects (a light blow with a stick causes irritation and a response in a person). The second type involves transferring meanings, psychological states, mental experiences (hitting a knight with a sword symbolized his elevation to the high rank of a knight and recognition of the high qualities associated with this title in him). Symbolic conductors are very important for the expansion of solidarity in society, but only if they express mental experiences in a uniform way and are interpreted uniformly by interacting individuals. A similar perception and interpretation of symbolic conductors is achieved due to: (1) the rebound effect of symbolic conductors on the psyche of people (cultural monuments, traditions, paintings, etc.), (2) the tangibility and visibility of symbolic conductors (common language, the same approaches to identification of mental states), (3) fetishization of a symbol (while the level of fetishization grows, its ability to unite people also grows).

The typology of solidarity proposed by Sorokin within the framework of the theory of the symbolic has become widely known. It opposes *internal and extended tribal solidarity*, the differences between them are based on the characteristics of the symbolic conductors and value systems. He emphasises that there are two ways how individuals perceive the nature of reality – *sensual* and *idealistic*. In the first case, individuals use their sensory organs to perceive and interpret material objects and do not see anything beyond the limits of sensual existence; in the second one – the same material objects are perceived by individuals differently, they are guided by reality, which is considered as non-material and spiritual (Sorokin 2006: 63).

The internal tribal solidarity is focused on intra-group needs, it is dominated by a sensual cultural mentality. Such selfish intra-group solidarity ensures the growth of well-being and at the same time the fetishization of generic symbols through confrontation and enmity with other solidarity groups, which leads to wars and an increase in social tension within society. The driving force that ensures unity is rivalry, enmity, the struggle for the possession of material resources, symbols of power, which have a positive meaning in the system of values of sensory culture. Solidarity groups care particularly about the private good, they are often in antagonistic relations, which does not contribute to consensus and agreement both within individual societies and in the whole world.

Achieving the public good, strengthening social solidarity, reducing conflict in society becomes possible due to extended tribal solidarity, which is characterized by altruistic behaviour towards other groups and orientation towards an idealistic value system (Sorokin 2002). As V. Jeffries writes, the integral concept of solidarity implies its understanding as a type of interaction aimed at goals that do not violate the good of people or the fundamental rights of the individual and the social order; it appeals to fairness for all participants of the interaction (Jeffries 2005). In other words, this type of solidarity is oriented towards the desire for love, justice, harmony and mutual assistance, which is more rooted in the human mind. Sorokin emphasizes that the adoption of an idealistic, rather than sensual, value system will ensure a longer existence for society. Attaining it means overcoming group egoism and forming an attitude of serving others and altruistic love in the society.

Altruistic love as the basis of social solidarity

The triad of social solidarity, altruism and love is the key to understanding the origins of Sorokin's social ideal. Social solidarity is a manifestation of altruism and love. Altruism is understood as the active position of a person, creative activity aimed at helping others against their own interests. For Sorokin, the study of altruism and love was one of the most important areas of scientific research, although it was traditionally believed that manifestations of altruistic love were the concern of religion and ethics rather than science. The kind of love that interested him in theoretical generalisations is *agape* – unselfish love. He argued that only accumulation and dissemination of the energy of non-egoistic love in society would prevent military conflicts

with catastrophic consequences for millions of people, as well as would lead to harmony in the social structure. Love favours the 'development of a healthy, whole and creative personality', increases the life expectancy of an individual, and also helps to resolve and prevent political conflicts, which extends the life expectancy of society.

Moreover, according to Sorokin, without increasing 'the production, accumulation and distribution of unselfish love, no other means can either prevent future suicidal wars or establish a harmonious structure for the human universe' (Sorokin 1997: 248). It becomes possible thanks to the following measures: (1) increasing the number of creative love heroes whose energy is able to provide the necessary minimum of solidarity in groups (Buddha, Jesus, Gandhi); (2) increasing the production of love by ordinary people and social groups (refrain from crime, reduce hatred, increase good deeds); (3) rearranging cultural systems to stop the flow of negative hate emissions, and only radiate positive experiences of love.

The energy of love thus accumulated in individuals, groups and institutions can become sufficient for solving the practical problems of mankind:

1) prevention of crimes, wars, revolutions and all those phenomena that are based on hatred, envy and misfortune;

2) maintaining the growth of the creative activity of the individual;

3) reduction and elimination of the worst forms of suffering, unhappiness, loneliness and premature death;

4) providing everyone with a holistic world, a friendly and spiritualized space (Sorokin 1997: 311).

In addition, altruistic love and, as a result, solidarity, according to Sorokin, saves an individual from disintegration with other members of society, reduce the likelihood of mental illness, and minimizes the manifestations of suicidal moods. 'When their close social ties are weakened or severed – with their family members or with other loved ones – and he or she becomes a stranger in his or her environment, then their sense of psychosocial isolation begins to grow, and the likelihood of becoming a victim of suicide increases', – notes Sorokin. 'Total psychosocial loneliness is an unbearable burden. For this reason, atheists are more likely to commit a suicide than believers. It explains why single people have higher suicide rates than married ones, and the childless families have higher suicide rates than those with children' (Sorokin 2009: Chapter 6).

Sorokin considers different aspects of altruism, highlighting its features as a social tool for initiating mutual assistance and support within the community, a means of strengthening social ties, a social norm that establishes a certain type of behaviour within the community, which people internalize in the process of socialization.

From his point of view, the levels of manifestation of altruism can vary from '*extremely minimal altruism*' to '*creative altruism*'. The minimum degree of altruism is manifested when an individual, exercising their legal rights and obligations, does not harm or violate the

rights and obligations of the other individuals. True altruism begins when the minimum level is overcome. In this case, a person demonstrates a willingness to sacrifice and sacrifices their legitimate interests in favour of another, refrains from harming another, even if the legal right allows them to do so, and provides help in various situations, although no law obliges them to act this way.

'Creative altruism' is by its nature close to manifestations of love. Sometimes Sorokin replaces these concepts with one another, uses them as synonyms, essentially equating them. Like love, altruism can be accumulated and shared. Both love and altruism predetermine selfless behaviour. Following this logic, we can assume that the level of social solidarity is the higher, the more members of society have crossed the threshold of 'creative altruism', have discovered the potential of active love in themselves, and are ready to support and help others on their own initiative, based on personal convictions, without looking back at legal prescriptions and existing rules of social coexistence.

Obviously, people are not born altruists, they become them under the influence of their social environment. Thus, people are divided into three groups: (1) 'successful altruists' who communicate with virtuous people from childhood, in the family they are instilled with a set of healthy moral values that are inextricably linked with love; (2) 'late altruists', who have become altruists in the process of a long and complex personality transformation, their values have undergone significant changes towards accepting love as the highest value; (3) 'intermediate altruists' who incorporate features of the first two types and wander in search of moral perfection; most people belong to this type.

In 1949, Sorokin organized the Harvard Research Centre for Creative Altruism. He proceeded from the fact that the development of solidarity ties in society was possible only if altruistic attitudes were consolidated and spread in the minds of people. It is impossible to introduce them by the efforts of the state. It has to be a purposeful cultivation in each individual of the values of humanism by the society, and transformation of altruism into a natural model of behaviour of all its members.

In this Centre, Sorokin, in collaboration with other eminent researchers, developed methods for nurturing altruism both at the individual and group levels (Sorokin 2002). An important step towards the *altruization* of society, according to Sorokin, is not only the scientific study of this object, but also the creation of an applied science of *amitology*, the subject of which should be love and mutual assistance in individual and intergroup relations, as well as the development of effective methods of altruization of society, the development of human abilities for unselfish, mutual cooperation to strengthen solidarity ties. He wrote that altruistic formation and transformation of human beings is an exceedingly delicate, complex, and difficult operation. There is no single magic procedure that can successfully help to perform it. Neither is there a standard set of operations equally applicable to all individuals and

groups. To be effective, the methods must vary in accordance with the many properties of the individuals and groups.

According to Sorokin's plan, the altruization of an individual should be carried out at three levels which are biological, social and mental. It allows to distinguish three groups of techniques. *The first group* includes techniques aimed at normalizing the physiological condition of the individual (motor and breathing exercises, physical activity, yoga practices, gymnastics, etc.).

The second group includes techniques that help to shape the social attitude of the individual and their motivation to follow the altruistic behaviour model in everyday life. These techniques are based on the main principle of behaviourism which is 'stimulus-response': using suitable incentives (encouragements, rewards, condemnations, punishments, etc.) under certain conditions makes it possible to achieve automation of the desired model of altruistic behaviour in an individual and increases solidarity in the community, to which they belong. This group also includes techniques associated with the socialization of the individual. One of the most striking examples is the reception of life experience. The essence of this technique is to place an individual in certain real-life conditions where they obtain the expected life experience. This experience will allow the individual to feel the importance of mutual assistance, support, self-sacrifice and accept them as the optimal model of social behaviour.

The third group includes techniques that provide in-depth understanding and acceptance by an individual of altruism as the only true model of behaviour, and transformation of altruism to the category of personal values. The mental impact on the individual is attained by means of persuasion, demonstration of vivid, memorable examples – heroism, patriotism, etc., as well as through creativity and art.

The complex implementation of all these methods fosters the physiological, social and spiritual readiness of a person to follow the altruistic model of behavior in society. At the same time, Sorokin prioritized the significance of the methods in the second group, paying special attention to the impact of rewards and punishments, or, as he called the latter, 'sanctions' on altruistic behavior and solidarity of representatives of various social groups. This issue is touched upon in many works by Sorokin. His first major work 'Crime and Punishment, Feat and Reward: A Sociological Study on the Basic Forms of Social Behavior and Morality', written by P. Sorokin at the age of 24, was dedicated to it (Sorokin 1999). Sorokin's main thesis is that 'the intra-group role of punishment and rewards is to create, preserve and strengthen intra-group solidarity, to prevent its collapse, to suppress mutual struggle and to bring its antagonistic elements to a common moral unity, which is achieved through training-ricochet influence of sanctions' (Sorokin 1992). At the same time, Sorokin idealizes the role of punishments and rewards in the altruization and solidarization of society, and even justifies their sometimes inappropriate implementation for these purposes: 'punishments and rewards,

although they cost humanity quite dearly, caused endless suffering, but still their main role within the group is to set, maintain and strengthen the unity of the group, the mutual consensus in the behavior of its members and the general solidarity of the group' (Sorokin 2006: 287).

It is not surprising that, adhering to this position regarding 'punishments and rewards', Sorokin included some additional techniques in the list of altruization methods that were very ambiguous. As the researchers of the legacy of Sorokin note, they are 'similar to totalitarian practices and methods of suppressing personality' (Dolgov 2014), so their implementation for altruization purposes has a number of limitations. The most striking examples of ambiguous methods of altruization are punishment and encouragement applied to a person and their relatives, public confession, meditative exercises, psychodramatic and sociodramatic techniques. Sorokin recognizes the limited possibilities of their application and even warns against their rash use. At the same time, he notes that these techniques provide an individual with unforgettable emotional experience, brings them closer to the acceptance of an altruistic model of behavior, they allow to influence the rational through the superconscious.

At the same time, if an individual or a group becomes the object of altruization, then the question is bound to arise: Who should play the role of teacher? From Sorokin's point of view, an individual is expected to practice altruistic love in social relations individually; religion may guide them. All main world religions contain a system of norms for managing behavior that promote the development of the individual, directing decision-making towards encouraging the common good, and the transition from selfishness to kindness based on love and virtue. In addition, all members of society must fulfill their social roles and professional duties guided by common, not selfish interests. Combining the selfless motives of millions of people will result in making countries and even the whole world better and richer.

Sorokin raised the question of the need to improve the production of love in society. The altruization of all mankind will ultimately lead to the creation of an *integral society*, the rapprochement of nations based on the development of science, technology and the great ethical systems of the West and the East: in the West – Christianity and philosophy, in the East – Taoism, Confucianism, Buddhism, Judaism and Mohammedanism.

Conclusion

Most of Sorokin's scientific works are permeated with the idea of social solidarity. Remaining in the shadow of the theories of social stratification and mobility, it can, nevertheless, be considered a key to understanding Sorokin's principles of human community and social development. It also reveals the specifics of his views on the mission of an individual, their interaction with their own kind. Following representatives of the Russian pre-revolutionary sociology, Sorokin considers solidarity a natural state of society, a factor of its development, and a necessary condition for effective social interactions. Solidarity is developed from below and stems from family, tribal, community ties. It is a

product of altruism, a person's love for their neighbour; it reflects the willingness to sacrifice themselves for the interests of others. The triad of solidarity, altruism, and love is the social ideal of Sorokin. Its importance for the development of society and the preservation of the peace of mind and even the life of its individual representatives, according to the scientist, is so great that purposeful altruization is required - at the individual, group, and society levels. The altruization methods proposed by Sorokin range from positive, reinforcing, inspiring the implementation of altruistic models of behaviour to negative, intimidating, forcing people to accept the altruistic conditions of human society. In the historical context, according to Sorokin, such adherence to the principle 'the end justifies the means' is quite justified: the unselfish love, altruism and solidarity bring people together, prevent suicidal wars, contribute to the harmonious development of society based on science, technology and the great ethical systems of the West and the East.

References:

1. Bakunin, M.A. 2016. Anarchy and Order (in Russian). Moscow: Direct-Media.
2. Dolgov, A.U. 2014. Pitirim Sorokin on Methods of Personality, Society and Culture Altruization: Social Solidarity and Altruism: Sociological Traditions and Contemporary Interdisciplinary Studies (in Russian). Moscow: INION, pp. 205-220.
3. Jeffries, V. 2005. 'Pitirim Sorokin's Integralism and public sociology', *American sociologist*, 36 (3): 66-87.
4. Kareev, N.I. 1914. Nature of the Historical Process and the Role of Individual in History (in Russian). Saint Petersburg: Tip. M.M. Stasulevicha.
5. Kovalevskiy, M.M. 1909. General Doctrine of the State (in Russian). Saint Petersburg: Tipografiya I. Trofimova.
6. Kritskaya, N. 1931. Apostle of Solidarity: P. Kropotkin and his Doctrine (in Russian). (<https://kropotkin.site/apostol-solidarnosti>) (accessed on 19 May 2022).
7. Kropotkin, P.A. 1919. Bread and Will (in Russian). Petersburg: Golos Truda.
8. Kropotkin, P.A. 1907. Mutual Aid as a Factor of Evolution (in Russian). Saint Petersburg: Tovarishestvo 'Znanie'.
9. Lavrov, P.L. 1898. Tasks of Understanding History (in Russian). Moscow: Izd. M. Kovalevskogo.
10. Sorokin, P. 1922. Main Problems of P.L. Lavrov's Sociology: P.L. Lavrov. Articles, Memories, Submissions (in Russian). Petersburg: Kolos, pp. 260-262.
11. Sorokin, P. 1992. Man. Civilization. Society (in Russian). Moscow: Politizdat.
12. Sorokin, P. 1997. Main Trends of Our Age (in Russian). Moscow: Nauka.
13. Sorokin, P. 2006. Crime and Punishment, Feat and Reward: A Sociological Study on the Basic Forms of Social Behavior and Morality (in Russian). Moscow: Astrel.
14. Sorokin, P. 2006. Social and Cultural Dynamics (in Russian). Moscow: Astrel.
15. Sorokin, P. 2008. System of Sociology (in Russian). Moscow: Astrel.
16. Sorokin, P. 2009. Crisis of Our Age: Social and Cultural Review (in Russian). Moscow: ISPI RAN.
17. Sorokin, P.A. 2002. The Ways and Power of Love: Types, Factors and Techniques of Moral transformation. Philadelphia (PA): Templeton foundation press.